

Acute Toxicity Evaluation of Methanolic Leaf Extract of *Putranjiva roxburghii* in Swiss Albino Mice

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Abstract

Putranjiva roxburghii is a famous herb that has a potent property of reducing inflammation, treating cancer, struggle against harmful microbes, and safeguard the body against harmful molecules. Thus, the study was aimed to determine the acute toxicity profile of the methanolic leaf extract of *P. roxburghii* and identify any acute adverse effects. Acute toxicity was evaluated in Swiss albino mice after a single oral administration of 2000 mg/kg body weight, with an observation period of eight days. Biochemical markers (ALT, AST, ALP, creatinine, urea, and uric acid) and hematological indices (RBCs, WBCs, PLT, Hb, hematocrit, MCV) were compared with the control group. A histopathological examination of vital organs, including the liver, kidney, spleen, heart, and lungs, was also performed. Biochemical and hematological parameters did not differ significantly from those of the control mice. Histopathological studies of the vital organs indicated the non-toxic effect of the extract. Our study indicates that the methanolic leaf extract of *P. roxburghii* demonstrates non-toxic effects and could be explored further for its therapeutic potential in disease management.

1. INTRODUCTION

The history of the human civilization has been dependent on the use of flora. Plants have been used as medicine by thousands of people over the years. It is important to use herbal plants as a means of treating and preventing diseases (Ur Rehman *et al.*, 2021). The association between plants and man has developed and most plants were turned out to be used as medicines. Phytomedicine or herbal medicine is the use of plants in medical and therapeutic purposes to cure and enhance the health of humans (Alajeeli *et al.*, 2023). *Putranjiva roxburghii* is a medicinal plant that is regarded in traditional medicine as a remedy to the most common problems, such as fever, colds, coughs, headache, and inflammation (Naik *et al.*, 2023). *P. roxburghii* Wall is a common source of the leaf extracts and seed bio-oil used in herbal remedies, Unani medicine and Ayurvedic

medicine. Its extract is used as a traditional treatment of elephantiasis (Gupta *et al.*, 2016). *P. roxburghii* seed extract was highly antibacterial and possessed potent blood sugar-lowering effects (Joy *et al.*, 2022). Phytocompounds denote common chemical substances occurring in herbs and are active and benefit human health as antioxidants, antimicrobials, anti-inflammatories, and anticancer agents (Alemán *et al.*, 2022). Other compounds present in the *Putranjiva roxburghii* plant are alkaloids, flavonoids, triterpenoids, phenols, phytosterols, saponins, fats, and fixed oil (Dar *et al.*, 2018).

The overall goal of *in vitro* and *in vivo* toxicity profiling of the methanolic leaf extract of *P. roxburghii* is to find out its safety margin and therapeutic window before the pharmacological assessment. Acute toxicity testing of Swiss albino

mice can be used to determine median lethal dose (LD50) and safe dosage ranges, and *in vitro* testing can be used to obtain mechanistic data on the cytotoxicity of the cellular level (Ahmed *et al.*, 2012). Although certain parts of *P. roxburghii* possess medicinal value, limited studies have been conducted on the safety of this plant. Accordingly, it is necessary to align safety and quality assurance practices to provide a consistent supply of quality medicinal plant materials (Chauhan *et al.*, 2022). The aim of this study is to evaluate the impact of the methanolic leaf extract of *P. roxburghii* on biochemical, hematological, and histopathological parameters in Swiss albino mice.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Collection of plant material

Leaf samples of *Putranjiva roxburghii* were collected from multiple areas of the University of Okara (Punjab, Pakistan). A taxonomist in the Department of Botany authenticated the species and a voucher specimen was submitted in the departmental herbarium to be used in future.

2.2. Preparation of methanolic leaf extract of *Putranjiva roxburghii*

Fresh leaves of the *P. roxburghii* were thoroughly cleaned with tap water. Then shade dried under room temperature. After that, an electric grinder was used to grind them to make a coarse powder and was sieved to separate large particles and kept in a locked plastic bag for further use. Preparation of the 75% methanolic leaf extract *P. roxburghii* was done by the procedure that is described in our previous paper (Nauroze *et al.*, 2023).

2.3. Toxicity profiling in mice model

2.3.1. Maintenance of animals

The experiment used Swiss male and female albino mice weighing 20-30 g and aged 5-6 weeks. All animals were handled and treated according to the recommendations of the Ethical Research Committee of the University of Okara, Pakistan. Mice were kept in the conditions of usual environment (23-25 °C, 12/12 hours of light/dark) and given unlimited access to food and water. Prior to the commencement of the trial, a

one-week acclimatization period was given to the animals.

2.3.2. Ethical approval

This experimental study was carried out with the consent of the Ethical Research Committee of the University of Okara, Punjab, Pakistan (Letter No. UO/ERC/2023/Z15; dated 22-12-2023).

2.3.3. Measurement of body weight

Prior to the experiment, the body weights of all mice were individually measured using an electronic weighing balance. Throughout the exposure period, daily body weight monitoring was conducted for both control and treated groups, and dosing was calculated according to the average body weight of the animals.

2.4. Acute toxicity study

The mice were split into two groups each group having seven mice. In the treated group, the mice were administered with 2000 mg/kg via gavage whereas in the control group the mice had unrestricted access to food and water. All mice were continuously observed for behavioral changes and signs of toxicity for 24 hours following dose administration, and thereafter once daily for eight days. Upon completion of the experiment, all mice underwent overnight fasting prior to dissection. The animals were anesthetized using chloroform and the sample of blood was collected through cardiac puncture. The samples were taken to the laboratory in two tubes in one being serum and the other hematological samples (Kanwal *et al.*, 2022).

2.4.1. Biochemical analysis

Blood samples were processed for serum and plasma separation following a previously established method (Nauroze *et al.*, 2023), and biochemical parameters (AST, ALT, ALP, urea, uric acid, creatinine, LDL, and HDL) were analyzed using standard diagnostic kits.

2.4.2. Hematological analysis

Examination of the blood samples of mice was carried out in EDTA filled tubes. An automated

hematology analyzer (Coulter Counter S Plus VI) was then used to do a complete blood count (CBC) with particular attention paid to red blood cells, white blood cells, platelets, mean corpuscular volume, hemoglobin, and hematocrit (Nauroze *et al.*, 2023).

2.4.3. Histopathological examination

The liver, kidneys, heart, and lungs were excised following dissection, and rinsed well with PBS (phosphate buffer saline). Subsequently, the organs were homogenized and weighed in grams in the weighing scale. Following fixation, the organs were preserved in 10% fresh formalin (pH 7.4) for 24 hours. The tissues were later dried in a graded alcohols (70%,90% and 100%) and then cleared by using xylene and embedded into paraffin wax at 58-60 °C. Sections were cut by a microtome and made into blocks as well as cut into sections 5 µm thick. All the tissues were stained with hematoxylin and eosin (H&E). Sections were stained and examined under a photomicroscope using different magnifications (Kanwal *et al.*, 2022).

2.5. Statistical analysis

The data were statistically summarized in terms of means and SEM. The data were evaluated using GraphPad Prism (version 5) and the t-test. Values that were statistically significant were those with P value below 0.05.

3. Results

All mice survived for an acute period of eight days after getting a single oral dose (2000mg/kg body weight) of the methanolic leaf extract of *Putranjiva roxburghii*. Monitoring of both control and treated groups were carried out carefully that shows no significant change in different behavioral patterns (Table 1). Both control and treated group mice were weighed daily. Table (2) shows that the control and treatment groups had no significant difference in their body weight. Mice organs (kidneys, liver, spleen, heart, and lungs) were surgically removed after the completion of acute period through dissection. These organs did not alter in size, shape, color, or composition. No significant variations existed between the organs weight of control and treatment groups (Table 3). The mice's blood biochemical profiles showed no significant differences in AST, ALT, ALP, Creatinine, Uric acid, Urea, HDL, and LDL (Figure 1). There was no significant effect of methanolic leaf extract of *P. roxburghii* on the level of RBCs, WBCs, PLT, MCV, Hb, and Hematocrit in mice's blood (Figure 2). The histopathological examination of the liver, heart, spleen, kidneys, and lungs of dissected mice was performed to ascertain the toxicity of plant extract. Histopathological analysis of vital organs revealed no evidence of damage, suggesting that the methanolic leaf extract of *P. roxburghii* was non-detrimental to these tissues. (Figure 3).

Table 1. The behavioral pattern of extract-treated mice observed during acute toxicity study.

Sr. No.	Parameters	Swiss albino mice	
		Control group	Treated group
1.	Lacrimation	Not Found	Not Found
2.	Drowsiness	Not Found	Not Found
3.	Nasal bleeding	Not Found	Not Found
4.	Convulsions	Not Found	Not Found
5.	Salivation	Not Found	Not Found
6.	Lethargy	Not Found	Not Found
7.	Mortality	Not Found	Not Found
8.	Food consumption	Normal	Normal
9.	Water consumption	Normal	Normal
10.	Body weight	Normal	Normal

Table 2. Body weight of control and treated group of mice.

Days	Body weight (g) of Swiss albino mice	
	Control group	Treated group
Before Dose	23.4 ± 1.4	23.9 ± 1.3
After Dose		
Day 1	23.1 ± 1.4	23.8 ± 1.5
Day 2	23.3 ± 1.5	23.6 ± 1.3
Day 3	23.4 ± 1.5	23.4 ± 1.5
Day 4	23.9 ± 1.3	23.9 ± 1.3
Day 5	24.1 ± 1.2	24.0 ± 1.1
Day 6	24.3 ± 1.0	24.1 ± 0.9
Day 7	24.0 ± 1.0	24.3 ± 1.0

Values are articulated as Mean ± SEM. Values are the mean of five replicates.

Table 3. Organ weight of control and treated group of mice.

Sr. No.	Organs	Control group mice	Treated group mice
1.	Kidney	0.3 ± 0.0	0.4 ± 0.0
2.	Liver	1.6 ± 0.1	1.5 ± 0.1
3.	Spleen	0.3 ± 0.1	0.3 ± 0.1
4.	Heart	0.2 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.0
5.	Lungs	0.3 ± 0.0	0.3 ± 0.0

Values are articulated as Mean ± SEM. Values are the mean of five replicates.

Figure 1. Effect of methanolic leaf extract of *Putranjiva roxburghii* on the level of AST, ALT, ALP, Urea, Uric acid, Creatinine, LDL, and HDL of Swiss albino mice in acute toxicity study.

Figure 2. Effect of methanolic leaf extract of *Putranjiva roxburghii* on the level of RBCs, WBCs, PLT, MCV, Hb, and Hematocrit of Swiss albino mice in acute toxicity study.

Figure 3: Histopathological comparison of vital organs in control versus *Putranjiva roxburghii* leaf-extract treated mice. Hematoxylin Eosin-stained sections were examined at 10 x and 40 x. Abbreviations: 'C' for Capillary, 'N' for Nuclei, 'ID' for Intercalated disc 'H' for Hepatocytes, 'S' for Sinusoidal cells, 'CV' for Central vein 'G' for Glomerulus, 'B' for Bowman's space, 'P' for Podocytes 'WP' for White pulp, 'RP' for Red pulp, 'L' for Lymphocytes 'E' for Epithelium, 'A' for Alveoli.

4. Discussion

The previous study conducted by Aslam and Ahmad (2016), suggested that herbal plants are an essential source of phytochemical diversity, which is the base of the pharmacognosy and the creation of treatment options. Their secondary metabolites such as alkaloids, terpenes and polyphenols have confirmed bioactivities such as antimicrobial effects, anti-inflammatory effects and are the foundation of both traditional medicine systems and drug development.

The growing importance of the role of plant-based therapeutics in contemporary medicine demands strict safety assessment of traditional medicinal plants prior to their clinical implementation. An example of a traditional Ayurvedic and Unani herb is *Putranjiva roxburghii* that has been used in the treatment of several diseases such as fever, colds, inflammation, and elephantiasis (Naik *et al.*, 2023). Although its antihyperglycemic and antibacterial activity has been proven before (Joy *et al.*, 2022), the safety profile of its leaf extract is yet to be fully developed. The objective of this study was therefore to determine the acute toxicity profile of *P. roxburghii* methanolic leaf extract in Swiss albino mice in accordance with the OECD guidelines.

In agreement to this study, previous research conducted by Panda *et al.*, (2021), they researched on extract of *P. roxburghii* Wall leaf. The research supported the presence of the antimicrobial and antioxidant properties of the *P. roxburghii* Wall., which may be attributed to the presence of bioactive compounds such as flavonoids, saponins, Phytosterols. We also noted that *P. roxburghii* has many biological activities that are more beneficial for human health and also for pharmacological activities.

Chauhan *et al.*, (2022), investigated *P. roxburghii* hydro-alcoholic leaf extracts on acute and sub acute toxicity in rat animal model. They provided an oral dose of *P. roxburghii* leaf extract (2000mg/kg body weight) to healthy mice on acute toxicity over a period of 14 days. The study revealed the absence of clinical indications of toxicity. It was expected that the LD50 of the *P. roxburghii* extract would be more than 2000mg/kg. We also studied an acute

toxicity of methanolic leaf extract of *P. roxburghii* on swiss albino mice. There was no significant difference ($P < 0.05$) in the in body weight, consumption of feed, and intake of water in all experimental groups in study conducted by Chauhan *et al.*, (2022). The experimental results of the biochemical parameters did not indicate significant differences between the treated and control groups. The histopathological study of the organs was done and no significant differences were observed between the untreated and treated rats. We analyzed the same hematological and biochemical parameters as in the previous study and observed no significant differences in their levels.

The systematic toxicity assessment performed in the study is necessary in determining the safety margin and therapeutic window of *P. roxburghii* leaf extract before this extract can be used pharmacologically. The lack of substantial toxicity in a variety of parameters, including behavioral pattern, weight changes, hematology, biochemical values, and histopathology, justifies the conventional use of this plant and presents a base to the further pharmacological studies.

Conclusion

The current study concluded the positive safety profile of acute toxicity methanolic leaf extract of *Putranjiva roxburghii* in Swiss mice. The findings established that the leaf extract did not have any significant negative effect on behavioral patterns, body weight or survival. Biochemical analysis reveals no significant variations in extract treated mice as compared with control group. Hematological examination did not show any substantial changes in RBCs, WBCs, Hb, MCV, or hematocrit. Histopathological analysis of vital organs revealed no morphological aberration in major organs which promotes the biocompatibility of the extract. Based on these findings, the methanolic leaf extract of *P. roxburghii* appears to be non-toxic and may be further evaluated for pharmacological applications.

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